

Synthesis of 2(*S*),4(*S*),5(*R*)-1-acyl-5-arylproline-2,4-dicarboxylic esters

Sharad Kumar Panday^{a*}, Jagdish Prasad^a and Dinesh Kumar Dikshit^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, M. J. P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly-243 006, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : drsharadpandey@yahoo.com

^bMedicinal Chemistry Division, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 20 October 2008, revised 8 June 2009, accepted 26 June 2009

Abstract : *N*-Arylidineglycine methyl ester **2** (Ar = 4-ClC₆H₄) undergoes base catalyzed [3+2] cycloaddition with (-)-menthyl acrylate to give the proline **4** that has been acylated with acetic anhydride and *L*-*N*-benzyloxycarbonylglutamic anhydride to the corresponding **1**-acylproline.

Keywords : Ester, synthesis, proline, acylation.

Introduction

Prolines/substituted prolines have been encountered as part of many natural¹ as well as synthetic bioactive products².

Non-proteinogenic prolines have emerged as important intermediates due to their use in the synthesis of conformationally rigid bioactive peptides^{3,4}, angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors and as pharmacological probes^{5,6}. Due to such a great value, chiral synthesis of prolines has received much attention in last three decades. Not only synthetic routes for the chiral synthesis of substituted prolines⁷⁻¹³ are available, but ACE inhibitory potential of *N*-acyl derivatives of substituted prolines¹⁴ is also well established. We report herein a synthesis of a 2(*S*),4(*S*),5(*R*)-substituted proline through dipolar addition reaction using a reported methodology¹⁵⁻²⁰ and its subsequent *N*-acylation.

The glycine methyl ester hydrochloride on reaction with *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde gave the Schiff base **2**¹⁵⁻¹⁷, which was reacted with (-)-menthyl acrylate **3** in the presence of lithium bromide and *N,N,N',N'*-tetramethylethylenediamine (TMED) in THF to afford the trisubstituted proline **4**. Similar results were obtained when silver acetate was used as a metal catalyst. The structural assignment of compound **4** was done on the basis of ¹H NMR and decoupling experiments²⁰, which were in consonance with the assigned structures and were supported further by IR and Mass spectra.

Our initial attempts to carry out *N*-acylation of the proline **4** with acid chloride were not successful. Acetic anhydride as well as *L*-*N*-benzyloxycarbonylglutamic anhydride in the presence of pyridine, however, brought about smooth *N*-acylation of **4** to give **1**-acylprolines **5** or **6** respectively.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Spectral data were recorded by using Beckmann acculab 1 (IR), Jeol JMS D

300 (MS); Bruker WM-400 (^1H and ^{13}C), Perkin-Elmer-241 polarimeter (optical rotation). Coleman C, H and N analyzer (microanalysis). THF and Et_2O were distilled over sodium benzophenone ketyl. Anhydrous N_2 was used for inert atmosphere reactions, glass apparatus were flame dried under inert atmosphere.

N-(*p*-Chlorobenzylidene)glycine methyl ester (1) : It was prepared from glycine methyl ester, hydrochloride and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde following a literature procedure¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

2(*S*), 4(*S*), 5(*R*)-5-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-4-menthyl-oxycarbonyl-2-methyloxycarbonylproline (4) : It was prepared according to a literature procedure¹⁵⁻¹⁹. The Schiff base 2 (4.2 g, 0.02 mol) was taken in THF and added to it TMED (3.32 g, 3.2 ml, 0.2 mol), LiBr (2.17 g, 0.025 mol) and acrylic acid menthyl ester 3 (4.2 g, 0.02 mol). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 6 h, progress of the reaction being monitored by TLC. At the completion of the reaction, the solvent was evaporated under vacuum, poured into water and extracted twice with Et_2O . The combined Et_2O layer was washed with 1 *N* HCl followed by saturated NaCl solution, dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated and purified by column chromatography using 20% EtOAc-hexane as eluent to afford the pure compound 4 as a white solid, yield : 4.5 g (53.4%); m.p. 100–102 °C; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 7.3^\circ$ (c 0.4, CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 1730, 1750, 2970 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 0.58 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 0.78 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 0.82 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 0.88–1.28 (9H, m, menthyl-H), 1.44–1.55 (1H, m, H-3), 2.35–2.50 (1H, m, H-3'), 3.32 (1H, m, H-4), 3.84 (3H, s, -OMe), 4.0 (1H, m, H-2), 4.38 (1H, m, O-CH), 4.50 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5), 7.25–7.35 (4H, m, *p*-Cl-ArH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 15.95, 20.59, 21.72, 23.06, 25.84, 30.90, 33.87, 39.75, 46.44, 49.06, 52.13, 59.68, 64.87, 74.20, 128.26, 128.52, 133.15, 137.59, 172.07, 173.38; MS (*m/z*) : 423 (M+2), 422 (M+1), 421 (M⁺), 363, 362, 282, 223, 211, 139 (Found : C, 65.20; H, 7.23; N, 3.52. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{32}\text{NO}_4\text{Cl}$: C, 65.55; H, 7.6; N, 3.3%).

2(*S*), 4(*S*), 5(*R*)-1-Acetyl-5-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4-menthyloxycarbonyl-2-methyloxycarbonyl proline (5) : The proline (4) (0.42 g, 1 mmol) was taken in pyridine (5.0 ml) and to it acetic anhydride (2.0 ml) was added and stirred at room temperature for 6 h. At the completion of the reaction the solvent was removed under vacuum. Et_2O (30 ml) was added and poured into water, Et_2O layer was separated and aqueous layer was again extracted with

Et_2O (30 ml), mixed Et_2O layer was washed with 1 *N* HCl (2 × 10 ml), saturated NaCl solution (2 × 20 ml), dried (Na_2SO_4) and purified by column chromatography using 20% EtOAc-hexane as eluent to afford the pure compound 5 initially as a yellow oil which on drying became a yellow solid; yield : 400 mg (86.3%); m.p. : low melting; IR (KBr) : 1660, 1740, 2980 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 0.4–1.4 (18H, m, menthyl-H), 1.5–1.7 (1H, m, H-3), 1.84 (3H, s, acetyl), 2.3–2.5 (1H, m, H-3'), 3.3–3.6 (1H, m, H-4), 3.72 (1H, m, H-2), 3.72 (1H, m, H-2), 3.85 (3H, s, -OMe), 4.28–4.45 (1H, m, O-CH), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5), 7.25 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, Ar-H), 7.55 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, Ar-H); MS (*m/z*) : 463 (M⁺), 420, 282, 224, 178, 139, 83 (Found : C, 64.45; H, 6.95; N, 3.40. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{34}\text{NO}_5\text{Cl}$: C, 64.77; H, 7.33; N, 3.02%).

2(*S*), 4(*S*), 5(*R*)-1-(*N'*-Benzyloxycarbonyl-L-glutamoyl)-5-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4-menthyloxycarbonyl-2-methyloxycarbonylproline (6) : Compound 4 (0.42 g, 1 mmol) was taken in pyridine (10 ml) and to it L-*N*-benzyloxycarbonyl-glutamic anhydride (0.26 g, 1 mmol) was added and stirred at room temperature for 6 h. At the completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed under vacuum, poured into water, extracted twice with EtOAc (30 ml), washed with 1 *N* HCl solution (2 × 10 ml), saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (2 × 10 ml) and saturated sodium chloride solution (2 × 15 ml) respectively, dried (Na_2SO_4), concentrated and recrystallized with EtOAc-hexane to get pure compound 6 as a white solid, yield : 400 mg (58.4%); m.p. 183–187 °C; IR (KBr) : 1720, 1740, 2975 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 0.5 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 0.75 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 0.85 (3H, d, *J* 8 Hz, CH_3), 0.9–1.35 (9H, m, menthyl-H), 1.5–1.78 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.0 (1H, m, H-3), 2.2 (1H, m, CH_2COOH), 2.45 (1H, m, $\text{CH}_2'\text{COOH}$), 2.60 (1H, m, H-3'), 3.52 (1H, m, H-4), 3.85 (3H, s, -OMe), 4.2 (1H, m, H-2), 4.38–4.50 (2H, m, NH-CH + O-CH), 5.1 (2H, s, Ph- CH_2O), 5.25 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5), 5.86 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, NH), 7.25 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz, *p*-Cl-ArH), 7.35 (5H, m, ArH), 7.58 (2H, m, *p*-Cl-ArH); FAB MS (*m/z*) : 685 (M+1), 684 (M⁺), 639, 284, 91 (Found : C, 63.06; H, 6.49; N, 4.4. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{45}\text{N}_2\text{O}_9\text{Cl}$: C, 63.15; H, 6.58; N, 4.08%).

Acknowledgement

The corresponding author is thankful to Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for providing infrastructural facilities to carry out above work, to SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow, for providing analytical data and to University

Grants Commission for financial assistance in form of major research project.

References

1. L. Radics, M. Kajtar-Peredy, C. G. Casinovi, C. Rossi, M. Ricci and L. Tuttobello, *J. Antibiot.*, 1987, **40**, 714, and references cited therein.
2. E. M. Smith, G. F. Swiss, B. R. Neustadt, E. H. Gold, J. A. Sommer, A. D. Brown, P. J. S. Chiu, R. Moran, E. J. Sybert'z and T. Baum, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1988, **31**, 875, and references cited therein.
3. J. E. Bell and E. T. Bell, "Protiens and Enzymes", Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1988, pp. 213-223.
4. D. J. Barlow and J. M. J. Thronton, *Mol. Biol.*, 1988, **201**, 601.
5. S. Thaisrivongs, D. T. Pals, S. R. Turner and L T. Kroll, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1988, **31**, 1369.
6. K. L. Yu, G. Rajakumar, K. L. Srivastava, R. K. Mishra and R. L. Johnson, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1988, **31**, 1430.
7. D. Seebach, M. Boes, R. Naef and W. B. Schweizer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 5390.
8. A. B. Mauger, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, **46**, 1032.
9. J. E. Baldwin, M. G. Moloney and S. B. Shim, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 1379.
10. E. G. McGeer, J. W. Olney and P. L. McGeer, "Kainic Acid as a Tool in Neurobiology", Ravan Press, New York, 1978.
11. D. K. Dikshit and S. K. Panday, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1992, **57**, 1920, and references cited therein.
12. W. Oppolzer and K. Thirring, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 4978.
13. P. Deshong and D. A. Kell, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 3979.
14. K. Shiosaki and H. Rapoport, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **50**, 1229.
15. O. Tsuge, S. Kanemasa and M. Yoshioka, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 1384.
16. D. A. Barr, R. Grigg, N. Gunaratne, J. Kemp, P. McMeekin and V. Sridharan, *Tetrahedron*, 1988, **44**, 557.
17. R. Grigg, H. Q. N. Gunaratne and J. Kemp, *J. Chem. Soc., Pt.*, 1984, **41**.
18. S. Kanemasa and H. Yamamoto, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 3633.
19. D. A. Barr, M. J. Dorrity, R. Grigg, J. F. Malone, J. Montyomery, S. Rajviroongit and P. Stevenson, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 6569.
20. L. N. Goswami, S. Srivastava, S. K. Panday and D. K. Dikshit, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 7891.